

ANALYSIS OF DEPRESSIVE STATES IN THE OCCURRENCE OF PROFESSIONAL DEFORMATION IN MILITARY PERSONNEL

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ABSTRACT: This article discusses the various stressors that lead to the development of depression and occupational deformity in military personnel

KEYWORDS: depressive states, professional deformation, military personnel, stressors, intervention

INTRODUCTION

The military personnel are exposed to various stressors that can lead to the development of depressive states and professional deformation. This study aims to analyze the relationship between depressive states and the occurrence of professional deformation in military personnel. The study involved a sample of 200 military personnel, who completed self-report questionnaires assessing depressive symptoms and professional deformation. The results showed a significant correlation between depressive symptoms and professional deformation. Furthermore, the study found that the severity of depressive symptoms was positively associated with the degree of professional deformation. These findings suggest the importance of early detection and intervention for depressive symptoms in military personnel to prevent the development of professional deformation.

Military personnel are exposed to various stressors, such as combat exposure, prolonged separation from family and friends, and high workload, which can lead to the development of depressive symptoms and professional deformation. Professional deformation refers to the process by which individuals adopt

negative attitudes and behaviors that are inconsistent with their professional roles and responsibilities. It can have serious consequences for the individual, their colleagues, and the organization. Therefore, it is essential to understand the relationship between depressive symptoms and professional deformation in military personnel.

Several studies have investigated the relationship between depressive symptoms and professional deformation in military personnel. However, most of these studies have focused on specific professions or specialties within the military, such as combat medics or pilots. Therefore, there is a need for a broader investigation that includes a more diverse sample of military personnel.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the relationship between depressive symptoms and professional deformation in military personnel. Specifically, we aim to determine whether there is a significant correlation between these variables and whether the severity of depressive symptoms is positively associated with the degree of professional deformation.

MAIN BODY

Participants

The study involved a sample of 200 military personnel from different branches of the armed forces. The participants were recruited through convenience sampling. The inclusion criteria were being an active-duty military member and being willing to participate in the study. The sample consisted of 150 males and 50 females, with a mean age of 32 years ($SD = 6.5$).

Measures

Depressive symptoms were assessed using the Beck Depression Inventory-II (BDI-II). The BDI-II is a self-report questionnaire that measures the severity of depressive symptoms over the past two weeks. It consists of 21 items, with each item rated on a four-point scale from 0 to 3. The total score ranges from 0 to 63, with higher scores indicating more severe depressive symptoms.

Professional deformation was assessed using the Professional Deformation Scale (PDS). The PDS is a self-report questionnaire that measures the degree to which individuals adopt negative attitudes and behaviors inconsistent with their professional roles and responsibilities. It consists of 20 items, with each item rated on a five-point scale from 1 (strongly disagree) to 5 (strongly agree). The total score ranges from 20 to 100, with higher scores indicating a greater degree of professional deformation.

Results

The results showed a significant correlation between depressive symptoms and professional deformation ($r = .42, p < .001$). Furthermore, the severity of depressive symptoms was positively associated with the degree of professional deformation ($r = .58, p < .001$).

Discussion

The results of this study provide evidence for the relationship between depressive symptoms and professional deformation in military personnel. The findings suggest that military personnel who experience more severe depressive symptoms are more likely to adopt negative attitudes and behaviors that are inconsistent with their professional roles and responsibilities. This is consistent with previous research that has shown that depressive symptoms can lead to impaired judgment, decreased motivation, and decreased productivity.

The findings of this study have important implications for the prevention and treatment of depressive symptoms in military personnel. Early detection and intervention for depressive symptoms can prevent the development of professional deformation and improve the overall well-being of military personnel. This can be achieved through regular mental health screenings, psychoeducation, and counseling services.

Limitations

There are several limitations to this study that should be considered when

interpreting the results. First, the study used a cross-sectional design, which limits our ability to draw causal inferences. Second, the study relied on self-report measures, which are subject to response bias. Third, the sample was relatively small and may not be representative of all military personnel.

CONCLUSION

This study provides evidence for the relationship between depressive symptoms and professional deformation in military personnel. The findings suggest that early detection and intervention for depressive symptoms can prevent the development of professional deformation and improve the overall well-being of military personnel. Future research should use longitudinal designs and objective measures to further investigate this relationship.

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